

Figure S1: Number of differentially expressed (DE) genes between organs of (A) TX2094 and (B) TM-1. The highest and lowest number of DE genes were shown in red and blue text, respectively.

Figure S2: Hierarchical clustering of expressions of transcripts expressed in *G. hirsutum* (A) TX2094 and (B) TM-1 organs and the floral buds of *G. arboreum* (A₂) and *G. raimondii* (D₅).

(A) All DE in TX2094

(B) Up-regulated in bracts of TX2094

(C) Down-regulated in bracts of TX2094

(D) All DE in TM-1

(E) Up-regulated in bracts of TM-1

(F) Down-regulated in bracts of TM-1

Figure S3: Comparison of differentially expressed (DE) transcripts between organ types in TX2094 and TM-1.

(A) All DE in bract vs. sepal

(B) All DE in bract vs. petal

(A) All DE in bract vs. stamen

(B) All DE in bract vs. carpel

Figure S4: Comparison of differentially expressed (DE) transcripts between TX2094 and TM-1.

Figure S5: The results of biological process (BP) enrichment tests in each organ of TX2094 and TM-1. * shows common BP in both accessions.

(E) TX2094: stamen

(F) TM-1: stamen

(G) TX2094: carpel

(H) TM-1: carpel

Figure S5: Continued.

Figure S7: Hierarchical clustering of expressions of *G. hirsutum* MADS-box genes. The color scale bar in the right, bottom corner shows high-expression (red) and no expression (0 TPM; blue). The subclade name was given next to *G. hirsutum* ID

(A) AP1/FUL – C-terminal sequence alignment

(B) AP3/PI – C-terminal sequence alignment

(C) SEP & AGL6 lineages – C-terminal sequence alignment

Figure S10: Expression patterns of *BBR-BPC* gene homologs. (A) Maximum likelihood tree of *G. hirsutum* *BBR-BPC* gene homologs. *AtBPC* indicates *BBR-BPC* genes of *Arabidopsis thaliana*. (B) Expression patterns of *BBR-PPC* homologs in TX2094 and TM-1.

Figure S11: Expression of genes related to flavonoid biosynthetic pathway (A) and their expression levels (B) in wild and domesticated cotton. wild = TX2094, dom = TM-1, *PAL*, phenylalanine ammonium lyase; *C4H*, cinnamate-4-hydroxylase; *4CL*, 4-coumaroyl-CoA synthase; *CHI*, chalcone isomerase; *F3H*, flavonol 3-hydroxylase; *FLS*, flavonol synthase; *DFR*, dihydroflavonol-4-reductase; *ANS*, anthocyanin synthase, *LDOX*, leucoanthocyanidin dioxygenase; *ANR*, anthocyanidin reductase. In the bar chart, each organ is represented by a different color: bracts = green, sepals = light green, petals = pink, stamens = yellow, and carpels = red.